

THE EFFECTS OF PROCESS VARIABLES AND REINFORCEMENT TYPE ON THE MAGNITUDE OF REINFORCEMENT - MATRIX - BINDER INTERACTIONS IN AGE HARDENING ALUMINIUM ALLOY BASED MMCs PROCESSED BY THE PREFORM INFILTRATION ROUTE

D J Towle and C M Friend
Cranfield Institute of Technology
Shrivenham Campus
Swindon UK

ABSTRACT

In liquid metal/preform infiltrated MMCs chemical reactions between the reinforcements and matrix alloys can occur during processing. Such reactions result in progressive depletion of alloy constituents with increasing infiltration. This paper describes the magnitude and effects of magnesium depletion profiles in two age hardenable MMCs as a function of processing and reinforcement variables. These have been measured directly by chemical analysis and indirectly by hardness measurements. It is shown that depletion effects are significantly reduced by reductions in preform silica content and by reducing the melt superheat employed for infiltration.

1. INTRODUCTION

In common with other MMCs manufactured via molten metal processing routes, MMCs made by liquid metal preform infiltration (LMPI) are susceptible to the effects of chemical reaction between its metal and reinforcement constituents. Such reactions result in chemical depletion of the matrix and in embrittling phases formed at the matrix/reinforcement interface. However an additional problem in LMPI MMCs is that these effects are progressive with increasing preform infiltration. The effect of matrix depletion is exemplified in age hardenable aluminium based MMCs in which the reduction in age hardening response with increasing infiltration can be clearly observed [1,2,3.]

The important chemical reaction in many MMCs is that between magnesium, a common constituent of age hardening phases in aluminium alloys and silica, present either as a deliberate binder addition or naturally in or on the reinforcement. Clearly key factors in the magnitude of magnesium depletion are therefore the silica content of the preform, and the time and temperature of contact with liquid metal. Some reaction between magnesium and the reinforcement may also occur, in which case the nature of the reinforcement phase will be important. Similarly the composition of the matrix may also affect the severity of reaction. Some of these factors have been investigated previously [1,2,3,4,] although generally few systematic investigations have been made into the effects of processing, reinforcement and matrix variables. A comprehensive analysis of these effects is presented in this investigation in which data is presented for 6061 and 2014 based MMCs containing fibre, or hybrid

particulate/fibre reinforcements. These MMCs have been produced by employing a variety of superheat/preform temperature combinations during infiltration.

2.1. Experimental

The MMCs employed in this investigation were based on 6061 (nominally Al 1% Mg 0.6%Si) or 2014 (nominally Al 0.5%Mg 4.5% Cu) matrices. These were reinforced with Saffil (ICI trademark) alumina fibre and with hybrid reinforcement consisting of either alumina or SiC particulates, dispersed by a small amount of Saffil fibre. Full details of Saffil fibre and hybrid preform manufacture have been described previously [5,6.] The particulates were of similar size, $\sim 15\mu\text{m}$, and morphology as shown in Figure 1. The Saffil fibre was $\sim 3\mu\text{m}$ dia by $\sim 150\mu\text{m}$ long and consisted of 95% alumina and 5% silica. Silica was also produced as a surface layer on the SiC particulates, as a result of the air sinter employed during preform manufacture. Unoxidized SiC particulate preforms were also produced by vacuum sintering. All the preforms were bound with ~ 1 to 2wt% silica (% of the fibre weight). The preforms were infiltrated at $3\text{mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ under a metallographic pressure of $\sim 30\text{MPa}$ in a cylindrical die preheated to ~ 350 to 400°C . The melt and preform temperatures employed for infiltration were generally between 720 and 750°C . Other process temperatures employed are given in Table 1 which also contains additional information on processing conditions.

Solution treatment and isothermal ageing treatments were performed in accordance with conventional heat treatment practice for the alloys. The 6061 based MMCs were solution treated for one hour at 550°C , water quenched and then isothermally aged at 178°C . The heat treatment/quenching practice employed for the 2014 MMCs was solution treatment for half an hour at 502°C , water quenching followed by liquid nitrogen immersion, and then ageing at 160°C . Isothermal ageing characteristics were determined by Vickers Hardness (H_v) measurement using 100N load and the through-thickness variations in solution treated (ST) and peakaged (PA) hardness values were also determined. The latter variations were compared with the variation in matrix magnesium content with increasing preform infiltration in selected 6061 MMCs. Other details of the sampling procedures employed for hardness and microanalysis measurements have been described previously [1].

3. RESULTS

3.1. Hardness and Magnesium Profiles

The variations in PA and ST hardness values with infiltration distance for selected casts of the 6061 and 2014 based MMCs are given in Figures 2 to 5, showing the effects of processing temperatures, silica content, reinforcement type and matrix composition. The PA hardnesses represent averaged values from the PA plateau of the ageing curves in order to reduce scatter in the data. Details of magnesium concentrations at different infiltration positions are also included in some figures and complete magnesium profiles are shown in Figure 4b. In all cases infiltration distance is measured from the surface at which infiltration commenced. This surface has also been referred to as the 'top' of the MMC. Additional information on the ageing properties of the MMCs is given in Table 2. The effects of the different variables are described in the following sections.

3.1.1 Process Temperatures

The effects of the process temperatures on hardness profiles is shown for the 6061 $\sim 20\%$ Saffil MMCs in Figure 2. The greatest decrease in through thickness PA hardness occurred for the

highest superheat temperature employed of 950°C, Figure 2a, (cast 1 in Table 1). This represented ~50% reduction in the age hardening response from the top to the bottom of the MMC. Lowering the superheat temperatures resulted in less severe PA hardness gradients with no loss of hardness in the upper half of the MMCs. Surprisingly there was very little difference in the PA hardness profiles obtained for casts 2 and 3 even though the superheat/preform temperature combinations employed were significantly different, Table 1. Magnesium analyses at different positions in cast 2 mirrored the variation in PA hardness, showing a marked reduction between 14 and 20mm infiltration. None of the casts employed for this part of the investigation showed much decrease in ST hardness. A very small reduction was observed in cast 1 of ~10H_v (maximum). No significant reduction was found for casts 2 and 3.

The hardness profiles displayed in Figure 2 demonstrate that reductions in process temperatures result in less severe hardness gradients for 20% Saffil reinforced 6061 MMC. However it is unlikely that these can be eliminated completely. Furthermore increasing the volume fraction of Saffil, see Figure 3a, increases the variation in through thickness hardness.

3.1.2. Silica content

The increasing magnitude of the PA hardness gradients with increasing volume fraction of Saffil, shown in Figures 2b and 3a, is possibly due to reaction between matrix magnesium and the Saffil fibre. However another possibility is that the apparent effect of volume fraction really reflects the increasing silica content of the preforms. In a previous investigation a link between binder content and hardness gradients in 6061-20% Saffil was observed[1] although it was not possible to provide a systematic correlation between these two quantities. This was probably because there were differences in the nominal silica additions and the amounts actually retained in the fired preforms.

This ambiguity in the source of interaction effects can be eliminated to a large extent by employing preforms containing mainly SiC particulates and carefully controlling the silica contents by oxidation[2.] Data for casts containing oxidized and unoxidized SiC is shown in Figure 4a which represents interaction effects resulting from relatively low process temperatures. Similar PA hardnesses were obtained in the first few millimetres of infiltration in both MMCs. However at greater infiltration depths the hardness of the SiC_{ox} (high silica) MMC decreased progressively with increasing infiltration distance, compared with no change in hardness of the SiC_{unox} (low silica) MMC. The low 'PA' hardness obtained near the bottom of cast 5 was unchanged from the ST value, demonstrating a total absence of age hardening at this position.

Magnesium concentration profiles corresponding to the hardness profiles for the SiC containing 6061 casts are presented in Figure 4b. These suggest a small reduction in magnesium from 0.8 to 0.6 wt% in the MMC containing SiC_{unox} after ~10mm infiltration. This compares with a steady decrease from ~0.6 to 0wt% in the 6061-SiC_{ox} MMC. Hence to a good approximation the magnesium concentration profiles mirror those obtained by hardness measurement. Furthermore both data sets demonstrate the drastic effect of SiO₂ on the loss of magnesium in preform infiltrated MMCs and consequently on the loss of age hardening response.

Different hardness profiles were also exhibited by the 32% Saffil (1wt% silica) and 32% SiC_{unox} (0.5wt% silica) hybrid MMCs, Figure 3a and 4a. The Saffil reinforced MMC also exhibited lower magnesium concentrations than the SiC_{unox} MMC, with maximum values of ~0.7wt% (at 2 and 6mm infiltration). These observations are again consistent with magnesium losses being associated with chemical reaction with silica rather than Saffil fibre.

3.1.3 Effect of Reinforcement

Neither of the hybrid Al_2O_3 or SiC_{unox} reinforced MMCs displayed any reduction of hardness with infiltration distance demonstrating that they were not seriously affected by chemical reaction of magnesium with either the binder or reinforcement. Observations on the Al_2O_3 particulate reinforced MMC using both matrix types provided further evidence that magnesium is not particularly reactive with this type of reinforcement during MMC manufacture. It must be noted however that the Saffil alumina fibre ($3\mu\text{m}$) was considerably finer than the alumina particulate ($15\mu\text{m}$) and also contained silica (5wt%). Hence there is a greater possibility of magnesium reaction with Saffil and this cannot be entirely ruled out.

A number of workers have suggested that the intrinsic strength of MMCs depends on their dislocation density. It is further suggested that dislocation densities depend on the physical characteristics of the reinforcement (morphology, size, thermal expansivity etc), for example see reference 7. There is evidence of physical matrix/reinforcement effects in the 6061 MMCs containing the higher volume fractions of reinforcements. The averaged ST and PA hardness values for the 32% Saffil reinforced MMC lies between the values for the 32% hybrid reinforced MMCs containing Al_2O_3 and SiC_{unox} particulate as shown in Table 2. Therefore the alumina fibre reinforced MMC appears to be intrinsically stronger than the alumina particulate reinforced MMC, even though there was clear evidence of magnesium loss from the former. Furthermore, comparison of hardness values from the top 5mm of the MMCs suggest that the 32% Saffil MMC ($H_{\text{ST}}=125H_v$, $H_{\text{PA}}=181H_v$) may also be more effectively reinforced than the SiC_{unox} MMC. However it is not possible to say whether this is due to differences in reinforcement size or morphology. It also appears from the data presented in Table 2 that SiC_{unox} particulate is more effective than Al_2O_3 particulate of similar size and morphology. This difference probably reflects the low coefficient of thermal expansion of SiC ($4.3 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$) compared with Al_2O_3 ($\sim 8.0 \times 10^{-6}\text{K}^{-1}$).

The effects described above do not appear to affect the age hardening potential of the MMCs. This can be seen from the 6061 MMC data displayed in Table 2. Apart from a small reduction in the value of $\Delta H_v(\text{PA} - \text{ST hardness})$ with increasing volume fraction of reinforcement, there is very little effect of reinforcement type on ΔH_v . The only exception to this conclusion is the particularly low ΔH_v value for the SiC_{ox} reinforced MMC, reflecting the detrimental effect of reinforcements containing silica on the ageing response.

3.1.4 Effects of Matrix

The effect of matrix alloy on the magnitude of matrix-reinforcement interactions is based on data from cast 1 and 8, for $\sim 15\%$ Saffil reinforced MMCs, processed with high superheat, and from casts 4 and 9, and 7 and 10 for the 30% Saffil, and 32% alumina/Saffil reinforced MMCs respectively, processed with low superheat. There was very little difference in the magnitude of the hardness gradients exhibited by the low volume fraction MMCs. Increasing the volume fraction of Saffil in both MMC types resulted in increased hardness gradients, Figure 3. However the 30% Saffil reinforced 2014 alloy exhibited much more severe hardness gradients than the equivalent 6061 alloys. These gradients were consistent with a much greater effect of magnesium/silica interactions in the relatively lower magnesium containing alloy. Nevertheless the magnitude of the gradient in the 30% Saffil 2014 MMC is difficult to explain, particularly since it appears to be more severe than for the 14% Saffil 2014 MMC. For example the minimum PA hardnesses were 167 Hv, for 14% reinforcement and 143 Hv for 30% reinforcement, at positions close to the bottom of the MMC castings.

Both the 2014 and 6061 MMCs demonstrated an absence of hardness gradients when reinforced with the Al_2O_3 /Saffil combination. The ageing curves for these MMCs, Figure 5, show a much greater increase in ST hardness due to reinforcement in the 2014 MMC than in the 6061 MMC. Similar effects are also apparent in the 15% and 30% Saffil reinforced MMCs, Table 2. However the hardening increment produced on ageing appeared to be less for the 2014 reinforced and unreinforced alloys than for the corresponding 6061 alloys as shown by the ΔH_v values in Table 2.

3.2 Ageing Kinetics

Ageing kinetics for the 6061 and 2014 MMCs, measured by the time to peak hardness, $t(\text{PA})$, are shown in Table 2. The data for the 6061 MMCs appeared to be relatively unaffected by either the magnitude of interaction effects or the volume fraction and type of reinforcement employed. All the 6061 MMCs exhibited considerably enhanced ageing kinetics, with an average ageing time $\sim 2.25\text{X}$ faster than the unreinforced alloy. Enhancement of ageing kinetics is also apparent in the data for the 2014 MMCs, although this was much less than that observed for the 6061 MMCs.

4. Conclusions

In aluminium alloy based MMCs manufactured by liquid metal preform infiltration, reaction may occur between magnesium alloying additions and the preform. The degree of reaction is primarily dependent on the silica content of the preform, present either as a deliberate binder additive or naturally in the reinforcement. Such reactions are typified by a reduction in matrix magnesium with increasing infiltration distance. 'Age hardenable' MMC's exhibit a reduction in age hardening response which 'mirrors' the magnesium depletion profiles. These effects can be reduced by employing low superheat temperatures for infiltration. However minimal interaction effects are only possible for preforms containing low silica contents. Other interaction effects in LMPI MMC's are related to the physical characteristics of the reinforcement such as its morphology and thermal expansivity and result in different strength levels in MMCs containing different types of reinforcement. Such effects are also strongly matrix dependent.

5. References

1. Towle D J, Friend CM, *Effect of fibre-matrix binder interactions on the matrix composition and age-hardening behaviour of 6061-based MMCs* J Mater Sci, Vol 27, pp 2781-2791, 1992.
2. Towle D J, Friend, CM, *The effect of particulate oxidation on the age-hardening characteristics of SiC/6061 MMC produced by the preform infiltration route*, Scripta Met, Vol 26, pp 437-411, 1992.
3. Decomps F, Gardiax N, Bader M G, Barbedo de Magalhaes A, *Heat treatment optimisation and improvement of tensile properties of fibre-reinforced aluminium alloys*, ECCM5, Bordeaux, France, ed. by Bunsell A R et al, EACM, pp 723-728, 1992
4. Lepetitcorps Y et al. *An overview of the damage effects related to the processing of aluminium matrix composites by liquid infiltration*, *ibid*, pp 657-663, 1992
5. Anon, *Preparation of alumina fibre preforms for use in MMCs*, Research Disclosures,

6. Friend C M, Horsfall I, Burrows C L, *The effect of particulate: fibre ratio on the properties of short fibre/SiC particulate MMC produced by preform infiltration*, J Mater Sci, Vol 26, pp 2651-1991.
7. Taya M, Arsenault R J, *Metal Matrix Composites - Thermomechanical Behaviour*, Pergamon Press, England pp 51-63, 1989.

TABLE 1 MMC-cast details and process variables

Cast	Matrix	Reinforcement		SiO ₂ * (wt%)	Infil Dist (mm)	Process Temps °C	
		V _f (%)	Type			Superheat	Preform
1	6061	16	Saffil	2	19	950	350
2	6061	17.5	Saffil	2	23	800	600
3	6061	22.5	Saffil	1	18	750	670
4	6061	32	Saffil	1	14	750	715
5	6061	32	Saffil/SiC(unox)	0.5	16	750	730
6	6061	32	Saffil/SiCox	5†	16	720	720
7	6061	30	Saffil/Al ₂ O ₃ P	0.5	15	750	750
8	2014	14	Saffil	2	15	1000	370
9	2014	30	Saffil	1	15	750	750
10	2014	32	Saffil/Al ₂ O ₃ P	0.5	15	750	750

* Expressed as the wt % of reinforcement

† Total SiO₂ content = binder + surface oxide (on SiC)

TABLE 2 Ageing data for 6061 and 2014 alloys in reinforced and unreinforced conditions

Cast	Matrix	Reinforcement		H _v (ST)	H _v (PA)	t(PA)min	ΔH _v *(ST)
		V _f (%)	Type				
1	6061	16	Saffil	94	150	300	56
2	6061	17.5	Saffil	90	154	260	64
3	6061	22.5	Saffil	87	153	200	66
4	6061	32	Saffil	121	175	300	54
5	6061	32	SiCunox/Saffil	119	178	250	59
6	6061	32	SiCox/Saffil	113	142	250	29
7	6061	32	Al ₂ O ₃ P/Saffil	208	169	300	61
-	6061	-	Unreinforced	50	119	700	69
8	2014	14	Saffil	129	178	1320	49
9	2014	30	Saffil	162	187	900	27
10	2014	32	Al ₂ O ₃ /Saffil	163	208	900	45
-	2014	-	Unreinforced	78	134	1500	56

* (ΔH_v) = difference between PA and ST hardness

Figure 1. Hybrid reinforced 6061 MMCs containing (a) Al₂O₃ and (b) SiC particulates.

Figure 2. Effect of process temperatures on hardness profiles in ~20% Saffil 6061 MMCs.

Figure 3. Effect of matrix on hardness profiles in nominally 30% Saffil MMCs.

Figure 4. (a) PA hardness and (b) matrix magnesium profiles in 6061 MMCs containing oxidized and unoxidized SiC particulates .

Figure 5. Effect of matrix on isothermal ageing characteristics of hybrid Al_2O_3 MMCs.